

Comparative Study of Tensile Properties of 17-4PH Using ADAM and Conventional Process.

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Abstract

This present work aims to compare the Tensile properties of 17-4PH stainless steel with two different processes. The first is the ADAM Atomic Diffusion Additive Manufacturing process, and the second process is making a sample for 17-4PH with a metal plate. Markforged ADAM is a patented process for Additive Manufacturing Process Metal Extrusion by Markforged. In this process, the 17-4PH metal powder is converted into a wire filament, and the filament is prepared with metal powder encased in a plastic binder. The ADAM process consists of three processes. 1. Printing, 2. Washing 3. Sintering. In WASH chamber filled with specific liquid under which green part is kept for dissolving the binding substance available in the printed part, leaving the part semi-porous so that the remaining binder may easily burn during sintering. This debinding step cleans your sintering furnace and purifies the finished metal part. The Sinter-2 fits the whole construction volume of the Metal X thanks to its sizeable active hot zone (more than 22,280 cubic cm). It's ideal for large-scale production or batch production. This heavy-duty furnace sinters a wide variety of commercial-grade metals from their brown (washed) state to fully dense metal pieces. The second Sample is made from a 17-4PH stainless steel plate. With the help of some non-conventional machines, the required dogbone shape for the tensile test can be achieved.

Keywords: ADAM, SLA, SLS.

1. Introduction

Due to this material's structure, it has corrosion resistance and high strength. 17-4PH has a small amount of retained austenite and large martensite. It is widely used to manufacture various parts, like nuclear reactor components, equipment used in chemical processes, and pump shafts. Now it can easily be replaced with titanium in aircraft engines. [1-2] nowadays, 17-4ph is the best choice for additive manufacturing due to its high strength and corrosion resistance. For all the additive manufacturing processes like SLS, SLM, ADAM.

Figure 1: Stainless Steel 17-4PH Chemical Composition

And upcoming future processes, 17-4ph is the first choice of all innovators, and many industries have replaced their material with 17-4ph. 17-4ph is a common name for the 630 stainless steel SAE type. It is also known as UNS S17400. The name comes from the fact that it contains about 17% chromium and 4% nickel by weight.

The basic instructions for working with and making 17-4PH are to react to annealing at 25 degrees Celsius (76 degrees Fahrenheit), hot forming at 950 to 1200 degrees Celsius (1742 to 2192 degrees Fahrenheit) [2], and aging. In limited form, it can also be cold-formed; stress corrosion resistance must be improved with re-aging. To cut 17-4PH, you can shear, band saw, or use an abrasive waterjet, but plasma machining is not recommended. [5] After discussing the composition of the material 17-4PH, we now know more properties of the material.

- **The Melting range of the 17-4PH is 1403.8 to 1140.04 degrees Celsius.**
- **The Specific Heat of the 17-4PH is 459.99 joules/gg K.**
The specific density of the 17-4PH is 7.79 g/cm³
- **The electrical resistivity of this material is 97.99μΩ cm**
- **The Linear Coefficient of the thermal Expansion at (71⁰F to 201⁰F) is 10.78 [μm/m.⁰C]**
- **The Linear Coefficient of the thermal Expansion at (71⁰F to 601⁰F) is 11.21 [μm/m.⁰C]**
- **Thermal Conductivity of 17-4PH at (@299⁰F) (@148.95⁰C) 17.91[W/m-K]**
- **Poisson's ratio (H900 Condition) of 17-4PH is 0.270**
- **The Modulus of Elasticity (H900 Condition) of this material is 196.9 x 102.9 Mpa**
- **The modulus of Rigidity in torsion is 67.1 x 103.02 Mpa**

Figure 2: Specification of 17-4Ph Stainless steel

2. Methods used for preparing the tensile specimen.

In this research, we are going to make tensile samples from two different methods

- ADAM.
- Traditional Manufacturing process.

2.1 ADAM

ADAM: - Markforged has launched a machine known as Meatal X. [14] It is a revolutionary machine that reduces the safety risk while working on the machine. It prints the metal powder, which is bounded by a plastic matrix. It enables new features like clouded cell infill for the reduced part. It is cheaper than traditional manufacturing, and also there is no wastage of any raw material due to this, the extraction of raw material from the earth is less by using this technology. This is reliable, affordable, and very easy to use technology. The ADAM process consists of three processes. 1. Printing, 2. Washing 3. Sintering. In WASH chamber filled with specific liquid under which green part is kept for dissolving the binding substance available in the printed part, leaving the part semi-porous so that the remaining binder may easily burn during sintering. This debinding step cleans your sintering furnace and purifies the finished metal part. The Sinter-2 fits the whole construction volume of the Metal X thanks to its large active hot zone (more than 22,280 cubic cm). It's ideal for large-scale production or batch production. This heavy-duty furnace sinters a wide variety of commercial-grade metals from their brown (washed) state to fully dense metal pieces

2.1.1 Basic specification of Metal X 3D printer

The basic specification of a metal X 3dprinter is that the maximum building volume of this printer is 11.8x8.7x7.1x inch, and in millimeters, it has a volume of 330x220x180x mm. [2-3]The maximum printing area is provided in this machine. The main benefit of this ATOM technology is the cost of the machine. In comparison to other technologies, this technology is much cheaper than others. The maximum size of the printer is 22.7x18.4x44.1 inches, and in centimeters, the machine size is 575x467x1120 mm;[7] the machine's weight is around 75kg or 160 lbs. it has a wide touchscreen display of 12 centimeters. It has an enclosed chamber with its environment to maintain its ambient temperature. The bed of this metal X 3dprinter has a unique vacuum-sealed print sheet that helps fix the printing part so that it moves while printing. This printer also has a heated bed like other regular FDM 3d printers. This printer does not require any leveling, or we can say it has auto bed leveling.

After discussing the build volume, machine size, and weight, it's time to discuss the other feature of the meatal X 3d printer; this printer has two nozzles. One nozzle is used for the metal, and the other nozzle is used for the released material.[5]The released material used in this machine is ceramic, which consumed on average one part of the release material used with the 10th part of the metal spool. In India required 220v Ac supply is to operate this metal X 3d printer. The main thing about the printer is what material can print with this meatal X 3d printer, and it can print the Tool Steel {D2, A2, H13}, Inconel 625, copper, and 17-4PH. The maximum size we may be able to print on this printer is 9.8inch X 7.2inch X 5.9inch or in millimeter 205X183X150 millimeter. The power required to operate this printer is a 220v A.C. supply (IEC 60320 TYPE C20). This printer also required the support material, and ceramic is used here as a support. The layer height is achieved by this printer, 50um and 125um. EIGER is cloud-based software that is used to print on this printer.

Figure 3: Process Flow Diagram of Metal 3d printer
(Credit: Markforged Inc.).[13]

2.1.2 Basic specification of Metal X 3D printer.

The Sample is the first design in Solidworks with the help of the sketch and extrudes command, and then it is exported in .stl format for further printing. The dimension of the Sample is 75mm width of the Sample is

12.5mm, and the thickness is 3mm.[11] After the design in SolidWorks, the Sample is printed in the metal x 3d printer, and this printer is installed in MedTech Lab IIT Kanpur under Prof. J Ramkumar after printing the Sample for 14 hrs. [6]The Sample is kept in Metal x washing for 14 hrs. During the washing, the binder particle is removed, which is mixed during the Making of wire. After the washing, the Sample is kept in a Metal X sintering machine. In this sintering, the Sample is kept for the next 30 hrs. We have printed 5 samples.

Sample Name	Angle with X-axis	Angle with Y-axis	Angle with Z axis	Sample formation
Sample 1	90 ⁰	0 ⁰	90 ⁰	<p style="text-align: center;">Fig 3 :- Sample direction for printing</p>
Sample 2	90 ⁰	90 ⁰	0 ⁰	
Sample 3	0 ⁰	90 ⁰	90 ⁰	
Sample 4	90 ⁰	90 ⁰	0 ⁰	
Sample 5	0 ⁰	90 ⁰	90 ⁰	

Fig 4:- Samples in Eiger software before printing

Fig 5:- Zoom image of Sample in Eiger software

Fig 6:- Capture during 3d printing in Metal X

Fig 7:- Capture After 3d printing in Metal X

Fig 8:- Capture After 3d printing in Metal X

Fig 9:- Sample in sinter machine chamber after completing the sintering process

Fig 10:- Sample after sintering

2.2 Traditional manufacturing

In this traditional manufacturing, a metal sheet plate of 17-4PH is used to make the tensile specimen. The specimen is cut with the help of an abrasive water jet machine. The machine is installed in Imagineering lab

IIT Kanpur The machine name is JET CUT 15B-15. The waterjet machine can cut up to 150mm thick of mild steel. The basic specification of the machine is listed in the table below.

S.no	Technical Specification	JetCut 15B-15
	Cutting Area :	
1.	Travel of X - Axis	1600mm
2.	Travel of Y-Axis	1600mm
3.	Travel of Z-Axis	251mm (Can be customized)
4.	Rack & Pinion Make	Gambini / Apex or Equivalent
5.	L.M. Guide Make	Rexroth (Germany) or Equivalent
6.	NC System	Power Automation (Germany) or Equivalent
7.	Software	Most 2D or Equivalent
8.	Traverse Speed	Up to 30000mm/min.
9.	Positional Accuracy	± 0.041mm
10.	Repeat Accuracy	± 0.041mm

Table 1: Specification of Abrasive waterjet cutting machine

Fig 12:- Waterjet machine installed in Imagieering Lab IIT Kanpur

Fig 13:- Close View of Waterjet cutting machine

The tensile specification is made with the help of a waterjet cutting machine. 3mm 17-4Ph plate cut with the help of waterjet cutting machine after cutting the process we get the desired the tensile specimen which is shown in the figure. The dimension of the specification is the length of the specimen is 75.0mm, the width of the dogbone specimen is 12.5mm, the thickness of the specimen is 3.00mm, the width of the gauge length is 4.00mm, the inner radius in the specimen is R4.0mm, and the outer radius of the specimen is R8.0mm. The dimensions mentioned in the above line are the same as those printed with the ADAM process. The overall dimension of the specimen by both the process is the same.

3. Result and Discussion.

In this research total of seven samples are created with two different processes; out of seven samples, 5 are created with the help of Atomic Diffusion Additive Manufacturing processes. Rest two samples are created with a 17-4Ph metal plate. Then these samples are tested in ACMS LAB IIT Kanpur. [9] Out of five samples that are 3d printed, two samples were distorted during the sintering process in metal X. The Sample that was distorted during the sintering processes is sample 2 and sample 4. The stress and strain curves are shown below.

The data we have received after the Making and the testing of sample 5 is given below.

Graph 2:- Sample 5 Stress Vs. Strain graph

Graph 3:- Sample 5 Load Vs. Displacement graph

The Above stress vs. Strain graph shows as the load increase, the stress rapidly increases up to 1.3 strain; after reaching the stress at 1050Mpa, the strain increases from 1.2 to 6.4, and after a specific limit, the stress starts decreasing, and the strain increases. The stress in the graph starts decreasing to reach zero at a maximum stain of 17.8. Peak Stress is 1030.986 MPa at a Peak Load of 12.99 kN, approximately 13kN. The 0.2% Offset Yield Stress 926.47 MPa, Yield Strain 1.08% Yield Load 11.674 kN, Elongation at Break (Using Strain) 6.48 %, the Area of the Sample is 12.6 sq-mm, and the Gage Length 12.778 and the Rate is 0.5 mm/min.

The data we have received after the Making and the testing of sample 3 is given below.

Graph 4:- Sample 3 Stress Vs. Strain graph

Graph 5:- Sample 3 Load Vs. Displacement graph

The Above stress vs. Strain graph shows as the load increase, and the stress rapidly increases up to 1.32 strain; after reaching the stress at 1008Mpa, the strain increases from 1.2 to 6.4, and after a specific limit, the stress starts decreasing, and the strain increases. The stress in the graph starts decreasing to reach zero at a maximum stain of 17.8. The Peak Stress on sample 3 is 1014.929 MPa at a Peak Load of 12.788 kN, and 0.2% Offset Yield Stress is 932.863 MPa Yield Strain 1.219 %, Yield Load 11.754 kN, Elongation at Break (Using Strain) 6.503712962 %, The area of sample 3 is 12.6 sq-mm and the Gage Length 12.566 mm Rate 0.5mm/min.

The data we have received after the Making and the testing of sample 6 is given below.

Graph 6: Sample 6 Stress Vs. Strain graph

Graph 7: Sample 6 load Vs. position graph

Now the Sample is tested, made from the wrought 17-4ph material with the help of a non-conventional machine. The Sample is created in the same dimension as 3d printing and has the same gauge length and width. Elongation at Break (Using Strain) 6.503712962 %, The area of sample 3 is 12.6 sq-mm and the Gage Length 12.566 mm Rate 0.5mm/min. The tensile stress vs. strain shows that the max stress is AROUND 1300Mpa

4. Conclusion

The ADAM Atomic Diffusion Additive Manufacturing process is a new technology in the field of the metal 3d printer. This is the first to use metal wire instead of metal powder, as in other processes. In the above research, we have printed samples in X-axis, Y-Axis, and Y-Axis, then we compare the result among five, and from the best of these 5 samples, we also compare the Sample with those samples which are created with the traditional method.

1. Sample 3 comes with the following results The Peak Stress on sample 3 is 1014.929 MPa at a Peak Load of 12.788 kN, and 0.2% Offset Yield Stress is 932.863 MPa Yield Strain 1.219 %, Yield Load 11.754 kN, Elongation at Break (Using Strain) 6.503712962 %, The area of sample 3 is 12.6 sq-mm and the Gage Length 12.566 mm Rate 0.5mm/min
2. Sample 5 comes with the following results. The stress in the graph starts decreasing to reach zero at a maximum stain of 17.8. Peak Stress is 1030.986 MPa at a Peak Load of 12.99 kN, approximately 13kN. The 0.2% Offset Yield Stress 926.47 MPa, Yield Strain 1.08% Yield Load 11.674 kN, Elongation at Break (Using Strain) 6.48 %, the Area of the Sample is 12.6 sq-mm, and the Gage Length 12.778 and the Rate is 0.5 mm/min.
3. Among five samples printed in the Markforged metal x 3dpinter, those Samples created parallel to the bed have shown the best result; the maximum Peak Stress is 1030.986 MPa at a Peak Load of 12.99 kN.
4. The Sample, created with wrought metal, has a maximum tensile strength of around 1300 Mpa Approx. So the printed Sample has the 80% of the strength of the traditional Sample.
5. It shows that this method may print any Shape, Size, and any infill can also be reduced by increasing the strength with proper design that can be achieved; in the future, it will also help in various industries like Defence, automobile, space engineering, medical, etc.

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A Brief Author Biography

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Experienced Design Engineer with a demonstrated history of working in the higher education industry. He was skilled in AutoCAD, Computer Numerical Control (CNC), Microsoft Word, Computer-Aided Design (CAD), and PTC Creo. Strong engineering professional with a BTech - Bachelor of Technology focused in Mechanical Engineering from Uttar Pradesh Technical University.

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Patents

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2. "CAPILLARY TYPE MULTI-JET NOZZLE FOR FABRICATING HIGH THROUGHPUT NANOFIBERS"
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